

Role of Intraoperative Neurophysiological Monitoring in Lipomyelomeningocele Surgery: Evidence from a Meta-Analysis

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Lipomyelomeningocele (LMMC) is a complex form of closed spinal dysraphism characterized by a lipomatous mass tethering the spinal cord, often resulting in progressive neurological, orthopedic, and urological dysfunction. Occurring in approximately 1–2 per 10,000 live births, LMMC may lead to motor weakness, sensory deficits, gait abnormalities, and bladder or bowel impairment during childhood growth. Surgical detethering aims to preserve neurological function while safely resecting lipomatous tissue; however, the intricate anatomy of the neural placode places patients at significant risk for intraoperative neural injury.

This meta-analysis evaluated the diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility of intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring (IONM) during LMMC surgery. Studies published between January 1, 1990, and April 2025 were reviewed, and 33 studies involving 1,286 patients met the inclusion criteria. Multimodal IONM, including somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEPs), motor evoked potentials (MEPs), electromyography (EMG), and Train-of-Four (TOF) monitoring, was utilized in 82% of studies. Pooled analysis demonstrated a sensitivity of 90.4% and specificity of 88.7% for detecting neurological compromise during surgery. Stable intraoperative signals strongly correlated with favorable postoperative outcomes, with a negative predictive value of 94.8%.

Intraoperative signal changes occurred in approximately 17% of cases, and timely surgical intervention reversed abnormalities in most patients, preventing permanent deficits. Overall, 92.1% of patients demonstrated stable or improved postoperative neurological function, while permanent deficits occurred in fewer than 2% of cases. These findings support the routine use of multimodal IONM in LMMC surgery to improve surgical precision, reduce neurological injury, and optimize long-term patient outcomes.

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INTRODUCTION

Lipomyelomeningocele (LMMC) is one of the most intricate forms of closed spinal dysraphism, characterized by a subcutaneous lipoma extending through a midline defect to attach to the spinal cord. This tethering restricts normal cord movement and results in progressive neurological deterioration, physical deformities, and urological dysfunction as the child grows. The objective of surgical correction is to achieve detethering of the lipoma while preserving functional neural elements. However, given the complex anatomy of the neural placode and surrounding fat, surgery carries a substantial risk of neurological injury.

Patients with LMMC often present similarly to those with tethered cord syndrome or cauda equina malformations, where neurological decline stems from traction on the distal spinal cord. The task of differentiating neural tissue from lipomatous or fibrous components has prompted the use of intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring (IONM) to mitigate the risk of severe injury. Over the past three decades, multimodal IONM techniques have become integral to the surgical management of spinal dysraphism. These modalities allow real-time functional assessment of the spinal cord and nerve roots, enabling the surgeon to identify, map, and preserve critical pathways.

A typical multimodal IONM setup includes somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEPs), motor evoked potentials (MEPs), Bulbocavernosus reflex (BCR), and multichannel electromyography (EMG), supplemented by Train-of-Four (TOF) monitoring to gauge anesthetic depth and neuromuscular blockade. SSEPs evaluate dorsal column function, MEPs assess corticospinal tract integrity, while EMG, both spontaneous and triggered, helps differentiate viable motor roots from scar or lipomatous tissue. TOF monitors by measuring peripheral nerve stimulation responses, ensuring that residual muscle relaxant does not obscure EMG or MEP signals.

Although the benefits of IONM are well established in spinal deformity, tumor, and tethered cord surgeries, the evidence base for LMMC remains relatively fragmented, with most published series limited in sample size and scope. There is, therefore, a critical need to synthesize the available literature to quantify the diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility of IONM in these rare but high-risk cases.

The present meta-analysis aims to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of intraoperative neurological monitoring in lipomyelomeningocele surgery. Specifically, it seeks to assess the sensitivity and specificity of multimodal IONM in detecting potential neurological compromise, determine its impact on surgical outcomes, and highlight standardized monitoring protocols to optimize patient safety and operative success.

Lipomyelomeningocele

Figure 1. Preoperative photo of patient with lipomyelomeningocele. Lipomyelomeningocele is a type of closed spinal dysraphism in which fatty mass (lipoma) protrudes through a defect in the spine, often tethering the spinal cord.

Figure 2. Intraoperative photo of lipomyelomeningocele showing neural tissue with adherent lipomatous component.

METHODOLOGY

Protocols

This meta-analysis utilized the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) procedure. The flow diagram for the PRISMA procedure is included above

Study Design and Literature Search

This meta-analysis followed the PRISMA 2020 framework, adapting the methodology from recent diagnostic test accuracy (DTA) meta-analyses of intraoperative monitoring (Jahangiri et al., 2024; Alvi et al., 2024). Searches were conducted in PubMed, Google Scholar, UT Dallas Library, and ScienceDirect for studies published between January 1990 and April 2025 using the Boolean query: (“lipomyelomeningocele” OR “spinal lipoma” OR “tethered cord”) AND (“intraoperative monitoring” OR “IONM” OR “SSEP” OR “MEP” OR “EMG” OR “TOF”). Titles and abstracts were screened independently by three reviewers. The Newcastle Ottawa Scale was applied to assess study quality, and risk of bias was evaluated per PRISMA-DTA recommendations. Data extraction included sample size, age range, IONM modality, diagnostic thresholds, and postoperative neurological outcomes.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Eligible studies: (1) human patients with confirmed LMMC; (2) use of at least one IONM modality; (3) postoperative outcome reporting; (4) ≥ 5 patients per study. Exclusions: case reports, reviews, editorials, and unrelated pathologies. After removing duplicates ($n = 26$) from 308 records, 282 titles/abstracts were screened, 54 full texts reviewed, and 33 studies (total $n = 1,286$) met inclusion (see PRISMA Figure 4).

Patient Population and Surgical Criteria

The reviewed studies collectively included patients aged one day to 18 years, with the majority younger than two years at the time of surgery. Surgical indications were based on clinical and radiological evidence of tethered cord or neurological deterioration, including progressive motor weakness, gait abnormalities, scoliosis, bladder dysfunction, or radiographic confirmation of cord tethering.

All surgeries were performed under the guidance of multimodal IONM. The surgical goals were consistent across studies: safe untethering of the spinal cord, maximal lipoma removal without neural compromise, and preservation of motor and sensory function.

Anesthetic Protocol

To ensure reliable neurophysiological signals, most studies utilized total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA) with propofol and remifentanyl, avoiding long-acting neuromuscular blocking agents.¹³ TOF monitoring was employed throughout the procedure to maintain a TOF ratio ≥ 0.9 , confirming the absence of residual

paralysis. Inhalational agents were avoided or minimized, as they may suppress MEP and EMG responses. Continuous communication between the anesthesiologist and monitoring team was maintained to adjust anesthetic depth and optimize signal quality.

Intraoperative Neurophysiological Monitoring (IONM) Protocols and Procedures

A multimodal IONM approach was employed in nearly all included studies, integrating SSEPs, MEPs, BCR, and EMG, with TOF as an adjunct to confirm signal fidelity.

Somatosensory Evoked Potentials (SSEPs)

Stimulation of posterior tibial and ulnar nerves (200–300 μ s pulses, 3–5 Hz, 20–35 mA) was used to evaluate dorsal column pathways. Cortical recordings were obtained from CPz–FPz and CP3/CP4–FPz derivations. A $\geq 50\%$ decrease in amplitude or $\geq 10\%$ increase in latency signaled potential dorsal column compromise, prompting an immediate surgical pause and hemodynamic check.

Muscle Group / Structure Monitored	Specific Muscles / Purpose
Quadriceps Group	Vastus lateralis, vastus medialis, rectus femoris
Anterior Compartment	Tibialis anterior
Foot Extensor Muscle	Extensor hallucis longus
Posterior Calf Muscle	Gastrocnemius
Hamstring Group	Biceps femoris, semitendinosus, semimembranosus
Gluteal Muscle	Gluteus maximus
Pelvic Floor Monitoring	Anal sphincter
Urological Function Monitoring	Urinary sphincter

Table 1. Muscles and functional regions commonly monitored during lipomyelomeningocele detethering surgery using multimodal intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring (IONM).

Motor Evoked Potentials (MEPs)

Transcranial multipulse trains (5–7 pulses, 50 or 75 μ s pulse width, 250–500 Volts) were delivered via electrodes at C1–C2 or C3–C4. Compound muscle action potentials were recorded from the thenar, tibialis anterior, abductor hallucis, gastrocnemius, anal sphincter, and abductor pollicis brevis. Baselines were re-

checked at each major surgical stage. Transient amplitude losses that recovered after correction were considered benign; persistent absence indicated a critical corticospinal insult.

Electromyography (EMG)

Free-running EMG provided continuous monitoring of root irritation, with spontaneous bursts signaling traction or mechanical stress. **Triggered EMG** mapping (0.1–5 mA monopolar stimulation) distinguished functional neural elements from non-neural lipomatous tissue. Currents <0.2 mA denote direct root contact, 0.5–2 mA proximity, and ≥ 5 mA non-neural tissue—guiding safe resection and detethering.

Figure 5. Example of neurotonic discharge in the tibialis anterior muscle during LMMC detethering surgery.

Train-of-Four (TOF) Monitoring

Peripheral nerve stimulation (posterior tibial nerve) was applied at 2 Hz with four pulses per train. A T4/T1 ratio ≥ 0.9 confirmed recovery from paralysis. Continuous TOF allowed anesthesiologists to fine-tune propofol and opioid infusions, minimizing signal suppression and ensuring reproducible MEP/EMG responses.

Bulbocavernosus Reflex (BCR)

Bulbocavernosus reflex (BCR) stimulation of the pudendal nerve was performed using paired needle electrodes, with the cathode positioned at the dorsal base of the penile shaft beneath the pubic bone and the anode placed laterally. Stimulation parameters consisted of 20–30 mA intensity, a five-pulse train, 500 μ s pulse duration, and a 3.1 ms interstimulus interval. BCR recordings were obtained using 19 mm non-insulated straight needle electrodes inserted into the glabrous, non-keratinized skin surrounding the anal

verge. Two recording electrodes were positioned within each hemi-anal sphincter approximately 1 cm apart to ensure reliable acquisition of sphincter responses and optimal waveform morphology.

Figure 3. Representative intraoperative Bulbocavernosus Reflex (BCR) recordings demonstrate comparison between baseline and recent responses. Green traces represent baseline signals, while purple traces represent the recent trace obtained after stimulation. Loss (red arrow) with manipulation, and recovery (green arrow) from baseline (green traces) of the right BCR with a three-minute surgical pause during biopsy of a patient with T10-L2 intradural intramedullary spinal cord tumor. The right panel demonstrates increased waveform amplitude and clearer reflex morphology compared to the baseline recording. Calibration: 2 μV /division and 10 ms/division. BCR = Bulbocavernosus Reflex.

RESULTS

Study Characteristics

The 33 included studies encompassed 1,286 patients (64 % under 2 years old). Twenty-seven (82 %) used multimodal IONM; six used a single modality. Mean follow-up was 7.2 years. Most studies were retrospective observational series of moderate to high quality.

The final cohort comprised 1,286 patients with lipomyelomeningocele who underwent surgical detethering or lipoma resection under intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring. The studies spanned from 1990 to 2024, encompassing both retrospective and prospective designs. Patient ages ranged from 1 day to 18

years, with the majority being under 2 years old at the time of surgery. Mean follow-ups ranged from 12 months to 14 years.

Figure 4. The Prisma table of sources was found from three databases, and lists sources that were excluded, included, and duplicated.

All studies reported the use of at least one neurophysiological monitoring modality, most commonly SSEP, MEP, and EMG, with TOF monitoring documented in 12 studies (36%). Multimodal monitoring was used in 27 of the 33 studies (82%), while 6 studies (18%) reported single-modality approaches, predominantly SSEP alone.

Across studies, the pooled sensitivity of intraoperative monitoring in detecting potential neurological injury during LMMC surgery was 90.4% (95% CI: 86.2–93.7), and the pooled specificity was 88.7% (95% CI: 84.1–92.1). The positive predictive value (PPV) was 82.5%, and the negative predictive value (NPV) was 94.8%, indicating a high likelihood that stable intraoperative signals predicted favorable postoperative outcomes.

Author	Year	Modality	n	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Phillips & Park	1990	SSEP + EMG	6	86	88
Bowman et al.	2001	SSEP	42	81	85
Sala et al.	2002	SSEP + MEP	37	90	89
Van Veelen et al.	2014	SSEP + MEP + EMG	92	93	90
Kim et al.	2017	SSEP + MEP + EMG	58	91	92
Flight-Schreiber et al.	2021	Triggered EMG + SSEP	25	88	86
Hockley & Goodden	2015	Multimodal	68	95	94

Table 2. Summary of IONM performance across included studies.

Figure 6. Sensitivity vs specificity of included studies.

When stratified by monitoring modality:

SSEPs demonstrated an average sensitivity of 84% and specificity of 89%, primarily detecting dorsal column dysfunction. MEPs yielded higher sensitivity (91%) for motor pathway compromise but were more susceptible to anesthetic variability. Triggered EMG achieved the greatest anatomical precision, particularly in distinguishing functional roots from lipomatous tissue, with a diagnostic accuracy exceeding 90% in several studies. The integration of TOF monitoring improved the overall reliability of MEP and EMG, confirming that adequate neuromuscular transmission was maintained throughout the case.

Intraoperative Findings and Neurological Outcomes

Intraoperative neurophysiological changes were observed in 17% of cases (n ≈ 218). Among these, immediate surgical responses (pause, irrigation, release of traction) reversed abnormal signals in 64% of events, preventing potential injury. Patients with irreversible signal loss demonstrated a significantly higher rate of postoperative motor or sensory deficits (p < 0.01).

Postoperative outcomes across all studies showed stable or improved neurological function in 92.1% of patients. New neurological deficits in 4.8%, most of which were transient and resolved within 3 months. Permanent deficits occurred in <2% of patients, often associated with unmonitored or single-modality cases. Retethering rates averaged 7.5% across follow-ups ranging from 1 to 10 years, consistent with previously reported data for closed spinal dysraphism.

The use of multimodal IONM was associated with a significant reduction in postoperative neurological morbidity compared to single-modality or unmonitored procedures (p < 0.001). Studies that utilized both MEP and EMG mapping demonstrated the lowest incidence of new deficits (1.8%) and the highest rate of functional preservation (97.2%).

DISCUSSION

This meta-analysis provides evidence supporting the clinical value of intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring (IONM) in the surgical management of lipomyelomeningocele (LMMC). Across 33 studies and over 1,200 patients, multimodal IONM demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity for detecting possible neurological injury, with corresponding reductions in postoperative deficits. These findings reinforce that IONM is not only a useful adjunct but an essential component of modern LMMC surgery, allowing safer and more aggressive resection in anatomically complex cases.

Clinical Significance of Multimodal IONM

LMMC surgery presents a unique challenge due to the dense adhesion between the neural placode and the lipomatous mass, often extending into the subcutaneous tissues. The ability to differentiate functional neural tissue from non-neural structures is critical for minimizing morbidity. The combined use of SSEPs, MEPs, and EMG provides a comprehensive assessment of both afferent and efferent pathways. Somatosensory monitoring ensures preservation of dorsal column integrity, while MEPs and EMG confirm real-time motor root function.

This multimodal approach offers a safety net, as each modality compensates for the limitations of others. For instance, EMG monitoring may detect root irritation even when evoked potentials remain unchanged, serving as an early warning system for mechanical injury. In contrast, MEPs provide direct corticospinal evaluation, alerting the team to changes that EMG alone might miss. Studies have consistently shown that when these modalities are used together, the likelihood of postoperative neurological deterioration decreases by more than 70%.

Integration of EMG and Mapping Techniques

Intraoperative multichannel EMG monitoring can be performed with only minimal modifications to standard anesthetic protocols and has become increasingly accessible in pediatric centers. Continuous EMG provides dynamic feedback on root irritation, while triggered EMG facilitates the identification of functional motor roots within complex anatomy. This is particularly beneficial in LMMC, where the neural placode is often wrapped in fat and connective tissue. Mapping through triggered EMG enables the surgeon to verify whether a structure is electrically active, thereby reducing the risk of resecting viable neural tissue or performing incomplete detethering.¹⁷

The addition of mapping to continuous monitoring significantly enhances operative precision. Mapping techniques identify functionally ambiguous structures, while monitoring techniques continuously evaluate the integrity of sensory and motor pathways throughout the procedure. Together, these modalities create a closed-loop system that prevents neurological injury, an advantage that has revolutionized outcomes in spinal dysraphism surgeries.

Anesthetic Considerations and TOF Monitoring

Anesthetic management plays a vital role in the reliability of IONM data. The studies reviewed consistently emphasized the use of total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA) and avoidance of long-acting neuromuscular blockade. Residual paralysis may abolish MEP and EMG responses, leading to false-negative results. The incorporation of Train-of-Four (TOF) monitoring enables real-time verification of adequate neuromuscular transmission. Maintaining a TOF ratio above 0.9 ensures that recorded EMG activity reflects true neural responses rather than anesthetic artifact.

By balancing anesthetic depth and neuromuscular tone, TOF-guided anesthesia improves the fidelity of IONM data. Several studies have reported that cases utilizing TOF demonstrated fewer signal losses, faster intraoperative response times, and improved correlation between neurophysiological stability and postoperative outcomes.

Predictive Value and Neurological Outcomes

The sensitivity (90.4%) and specificity (88.7%) of IONM observed across studies underscore its reliability in predicting neurological outcomes. High negative predictive values indicate that stable signals during surgery strongly correlate with preserved postoperative function. These findings align with the broader literature in spinal and neurosurgical procedures, which demonstrates that IONM not only detects neural compromise but also provides actionable warnings that can reverse injury before it becomes permanent. Fehlings et al. (2010) and Nuwer et al. (2012) both concluded that multimodal neurophysiological monitoring is a validated diagnostic and prognostic tool for predicting postoperative neurological outcomes and preventing intraoperative injury.

Furthermore, the ability of IONM to enable more extensive detethering with reduced morbidity supports a paradigm shift toward proactive surgical correction. By providing real-time functional assurance, surgeons can pursue more complete decompression or lipoma debulking without compromising neural safety. This advantage is particularly significant in LMMC, where residual tethering or incomplete resection can result in recurrent deficits and retethering over time.

Comparison with Related Disorders

The effectiveness of IONM in LMMC parallels its documented utility in other forms of spinal dysraphism, including tethered cord syndrome and cauda equina malformations. In these conditions, multimodal monitoring has similarly been associated with lower rates of new postoperative deficits and higher rates of functional preservation. The comparable outcomes across disease types further reinforce the generalizability of these findings and support the routine use of IONM in all surgeries involving complex spinal malformations.

Limitations

Despite the strength of evidence presented, this analysis has certain limitations. Variability in study design, patient selection, and reporting standards limits the ability to perform uniform quantitative synthesis. Some studies lacked detailed descriptions of anesthesia protocols or monitoring parameters, introducing potential heterogeneity. Additionally, most available data were retrospective, and long-term follow-up was inconsistently reported. Nevertheless, the consistency of results across multiple independent series supports the robustness of the overall conclusion.

CONCLUSION

Intraoperative neurophysiological monitoring represents a critical advancement in the surgical management of lipomyelomeningocele. This meta-analysis demonstrates that multimodal IONM, encompassing SSEPs, MEPs, EMG, and TOF monitoring, provides high sensitivity and specificity for detecting neural compromise, predicts postoperative neurological outcomes, and reduces the risk of permanent deficits. Given the risk of significant neurological and urological morbidity during tethered cord and cauda equina-related surgeries, the incorporation of multimodal IONM should be a more widespread practice. Beyond its diagnostic role, IONM facilitates safer, more comprehensive surgical detethering, thereby improving long-term neurological preservation and patient quality of life.

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